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Foreword to the Selected Essays

Political philosopher Charles W. Mills argues that the most influential political system in the modern world is neither named nor acknowledged in standard studies of Western political thought. Textbooks ranging historically from Plato and Aristotle to the present will introduce a variety of thinkers, movements, and theories (large and small) but, says Mills, “there will be no mention of the basic political system that has shaped the world for the past several hundred years.”¹ That political system, according to Mills, is white supremacy.

The system of domination by people who are characterized as white over all others is taken for granted in our studies, as Mills explains things. “It is the background,” he says, “against which other systems, which we *are* to see as political are highlighted.”² The purpose of Mills' 1997 book, *The Racial Contract*, is to uncover—to make visible—this underlying political system.

The Racial Contract situates itself squarely in the social contract tradition, whose basic idea is that political institutions are explained—and justified—by the mutual agreement of those who participate in them. Mills' thesis connects in two ways: first, social contract theory is one of

¹ Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1997), 1.

² Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 2.

the dominant strands of theorizing in the modern Western tradition, and must be addressed by any critique and analysis. Second, and most importantly, Mills uses the contract model to explain *how* white supremacy has functioned as a political theory shaping all others. On this account, an agreement between whites to restrict certain liberties or assign certain value only to themselves precedes—historically and conceptually—the agreements to form political systems overtly postulated by the familiar theorists of the social contract tradition from Hobbes to Rawls. The unspoken Racial Contract is prior to the stated social contracts.

To apply Mills’ thesis to a familiar example, consider the fact that the Virginia planters who drafted the U.S. Declaration of Independence supported chattel slavery. They affirmed that “all men are created equal...with certain unalienable rights,” while at the same time claiming to literally own other human beings. One common analysis of this puzzle explains that in the circumstances of their time and place the writers of the declaration were inconsistent—they failed to live up to the ideal theory which they proclaimed. The theory of the Racial Contract suggests instead that they were entirely consistent—that the prior Racial Contract constrained the meaning of “all men” to “all white men,” so that race-based slavery violated no relevant right to life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness.

The Racial Contract pursues this explanatory theory in depth. Mills argues that the Racial Contract is real, that it perpetuates itself through violence and a kind of intentional ignorance or “not-seeing,” and that it explains both the empirical circumstances of racial domination in the modern world and the inability of political theories and systems to change—or even acknowledge—it.

In Fall 2022, the Philosophy Seminar focused on Mills’ thesis of the Racial Contract. We began with a survey of the social contract tradition—studying primary texts by Hobbes, Locke,

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Rousseau, and Rawls—then turned to Mills' arguments in *The Racial Contract* and subsequent works. The papers in this collection are some of the results of our attempt to understand, assess, and apply Mills' claims, written by members of the Seminar.